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Guidelines on the use of generative Artificial Intelligence at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin

Museum für Naturkunde Berlin
Leibniz-Institut für Evolutions- und Biodiversitätsforschung

Preamble.....	3
1. Our aim: enabling AI	3
2. What is artificial intelligence?	3
3. Human responsibility.....	4
Legal framework.....	4
Recommendations.....	4
4. Protect personal data	4
Legal framework.....	4
Recommendations.....	5
5. Using AI at the MfN	5
Legal framework.....	5
Recommendations.....	6
Examples.....	6
6. AI has many faces.....	6
Legal framework.....	6
Recommendations for action	7
Examples.....	7
7. Development of in-house AI systems	8
8. For an open museum	8
Legal framework.....	8
Recommendations.....	8
Examples.....	8
9. Developing together	9
10. Validity	9

Preamble

The Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (MfN) is an international institution dedicated to research, collections, education and public engagement. It stands for scientific excellence, openness, dialogue and social responsibility. The responsible use of new technologies is part of this self-image.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is fundamentally changing working practices in science, culture and administration. At the MfN, AI is used both as a supportive tool in day-to-day work and as the subject of independent research and development. This guideline takes both perspectives into account.

1. Our aim: enabling AI

This policy sets out the principles, rules and responsibilities for the use of AI systems at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin. It applies to all staff members, visiting researchers, volunteers and other persons working at the MFN who have IT access. The policy pursues three equally important objectives:

- Enabling the reflective and productive use of AI
- Ensuring compliance with legal requirements (in particular the GDPR and the EU AI Regulation)
- Upholding scientific, ethical and institutional standards

The policy supplements existing regulations (e.g. data protection, IT security, good scientific practice) and does not replace them.

This guideline is a living document and will be regularly reviewed and updated. Feedback from practitioners is expressly encouraged. Please send any feedback or suggestions to: kiag@mf.n.berlin.

2. What is artificial intelligence?

Artificial intelligence refers to machine-based systems that can generate content, predictions, recommendations or decisions based on data.

To narrow the scope of the topic to the area relevant to your work, this guideline will focus on “generative AI”. This refers to AI that creates something new by utilising existing knowledge acquired through training (e.g., text, image, audio or code generation).

The guideline does cover analytical AI systems (e.g., pattern recognition, classification) and research-oriented AI systems (e.g., model training, high-performance AI) only within the framework of general regulations.

Internal and External Providers

Below, we define “internal” and “external” providers of AI:

By “external”, we refer here to commercial providers such as OpenAI, Anthropic or Google, which have their own terms and conditions or privacy policies governing the use of their services, which may not necessarily be acceptable to us.

“Internal” providers are those acting on behalf of the MfN and having entered into specific agreements with the institution.

3. Human responsibility

AI systems are statistical models that generate probabilities based on training data. They have no understanding of technical, legal or institutional contexts and may contain systematic biases or outdated information. Furthermore, recommendations and assessments by AI systems may prove inappropriate in specific situations and lack the necessary empathy. In the scientific, administrative and public context of the MfN, particular care is therefore required to avoid wrong decisions, damage to reputation or legal infringements.

Legal framework

- Decisions with technical, legal or organisational implications must not be made solely on the basis of AI-generated content. Ultimate responsibility always remains with a natural person.
- AI-generated content must be checked for potential legal infringements (in particular copyright, trademark and personality rights) prior to publication or dissemination.
- AI-generated content may be incorrect, out of date, distorted or entirely fabricated (hallucinations/bias). These risks must be taken into account whenever the content is used.

Recommendations

- Use AI primarily as a support tool (e.g., for drafts, structuring, idea generation, preliminary analyses), not as a decision-making authority.
- Verify key statements, figures, quotations and source references independently using reliable primary sources.
- Preferably use AI where technical plausibility checks by you or other staff are possible and realistic.
- For critical content, document how the technical review was carried out, particularly for publications or decision-making documents.
- Be vigilant against attempts at manipulation (e.g., 'prompt injection' via hidden instructions in websites or documents). Question AI prompts asking you to enter additional data or click on links, and do not copy content from external sources into prompts without checking it first.

4. Protect personal data

Many AI applications are operated by external AI providers who may not be GDPR-compliant. This can lead to data breaches. Even seemingly harmless information can, when combined, enable the identification of individuals. Therefore, the responsible handling of personal and personally identifiable data is essential.

Legal framework

- When using AI systems, the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) must be complied with.
- Sensitive personal data within the meaning of Article 9 of the GDPR must not be processed or entered into AI systems.

- Personnel, application, health or performance data must not be entered into or processed in external AI systems.
- Personal data may only be processed if there is a legal basis for doing so and the processing is permitted under data protection law.

Recommendations

- Prioritise internal AI services: For work-related purposes, use internal, data-protected AI services. These offer a higher level of data security, albeit not unlimited. As a general rule, assume that external AI systems are not suitable for processing personal data.
- No sensitive personnel data in AI systems: In particular, do not process sensitive personal data (Art. 9 GDPR) or any personnel, application, health or performance data in external AI systems.
- Minimise personal references (anonymise/pseudonymise): Consistently remove personal details before inputting them, or replace them with placeholders, pseudonyms or dummy data (e.g. 'Person A' instead of a real name). Also check whether combinations of details could indirectly enable identification.
- Prompts without confidential information or secrets: Do not transmit any confidential information, trade or business secrets, or content subject to contractual confidentiality obligations in prompts.
- Check copyright before entering prompts: Do not use copyright-protected works or third-party content (e.g. texts, images, code) in prompts unless you hold the necessary usage rights or licences. Pay particular attention to any restrictions imposed by publishers, journals or data providers.
- Check AI outputs for personal data: Before reusing AI outputs, check whether they contain personal data and, if necessary, delete or anonymise it.
- Seek advice if in doubt: If in doubt, use preferably internal AI services or seek data protection advice from the in-house "AI Working Group (KI-AG)" (ki-ag@mfn.berlin) or contact the data protection officers.

5. Using AI at the MfN

External AI services are largely beyond the technical and organisational control of the MfN. This increases the risk of data processing and data transfers that are inadmissible under data protection law (e.g., through logging, further processing or involvement of third countries).

The MfN therefore prioritises internal, data-protected and access-restricted solutions for common use cases and is gradually expanding these. A data-protected, access-restricted chatbot interface is currently available for this purpose, which can be used with various large language models (LLMs).

Legal framework

- For official purposes, internally provided AI services must generally be used.
- External AI services may only be used for work-related purposes if (a) no internal service is available and (b) the tool or tool category has been approved for the intended purpose.

For tools that have not been approved, prior consultation with and approval by the relevant bodies (KI-AG) is required.

- AI services must be used for work purposes exclusively via work accounts provided or approved for this purpose. The use of private accounts for work purposes and the use of work accounts for private purposes are prohibited. The independent creation of work accounts with external providers is not permitted. Login details must be treated as confidential and must not be disclosed.

Recommendations

- Use internal AI services, particularly for internal, non-public or sensitive content.
- If no internal service is available, use external AI services only for clearly non-critical purposes without any reference to individuals and without internal/non-public content, exclusively via work accounts and within the scope of authorisations; in all other cases, prior authorisation must be obtained.
- When using external tools, always assume that inputs (including metadata) are processed outside the direct control of the MfN and that there is therefore an increased data protection risk.
- Do not process any internal, non-public or personal data via external AI services.

Examples

- An internal draft concept is edited via the internal chatbot interface, not via an external tool.
- For brainstorming on general topics, an external AI service may be used on an exceptional basis – subject to approval and without any reference to data.
- New AI tools are reviewed and approved by KI-AG and IT before being put into productive use.

6. AI has many faces

The use of AI varies considerably depending on the institutional context. Research, collections, education and administration are subject to different professional, ethical and legal requirements. This distinction is necessary to ensure academic integrity, institutional credibility, and compliance with data protection and administrative requirements. The specific use cases listed below illustrate the framework for various contexts and should not be regarded as exhaustive.

Legal framework

- The use of AI in scientific publications must be disclosed.
- AI systems must not be listed as authors.
- AI must not be used for the covert generation or manipulation of primary research data.
- Guidelines from publishers, journals and data providers regarding the use of AI (e.g. uploading, processing, analysis) must be checked in advance and adhered to.
- The use of external AI tools in the review/peer-review process is not permitted unless the confidentiality of submissions can be guaranteed.

- Substantive and editorial decisions shall always remain with the responsible staff members.
- AI-generated data, e.g. from text recognition processes, must be clearly identified as such
- Content with external impact must be subject to professional oversight and editorial review.
- Automated personnel decisions or performance assessments using AI are not permitted.

Recommendations for action

- Use AI
 - for research, structuring and preliminary analyses, not for the covert generation of research data,
 - to assist with data extraction and annotation,
 - for linguistic revision, support and translation,
 - for general process support.
- Verify AI-generated content against the original sources.
- Do not make technical decisions automatically based on AI outputs.
- Ensure that content is editorially reviewed before publication.
- Do not use AI to evaluate or make decisions about individuals.
- Document the use of AI in research projects transparently. The following information must be provided: name, version and provider of the AI model used, period of use, description of the purpose of use (text generation, summarisation, translation, research, text revision, etc.), reference to this guideline
- Example: The creation of this text was supported between ... and ... by the following AI services for the generation of prompts, text, text analysis, structuring and optimisation, and proofreading: ChatGPT o3-mini & GPT-4o from OpenAI, Claude Sonnet 3.5 & 3.7 from Anthropic. In doing so, the “Guidelines on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) at the Museum für Naturkunde Berlin”, <https://doi.org/10.7479/7tt3-rs54>, have been taken into account.
- When using text and data mining (TDM), please ensure that the works/data used are lawfully accessible and that their use complies with applicable copyright regulations.

Examples

- AI is used for literature research and the initial structuring of texts.
- AI is used to summarise meeting minutes.
- AI assists with automatic tagging; responsibility for the accuracy of the data remains with the relevant specialist at .
- AI-assisted translations are subject to expert review.
- AI assists in the creation of drafts for internal correspondence, which are subsequently reviewed.

- AI-generated draft texts for public relations are edited and approved.
- AI is used to generate conceptual ideas, which are subsequently developed in more detail by subject matter experts.
- The use of AI tools is disclosed in the methods section or in the acknowledgements.
- AI-generated summaries are compared with the original publications.

7. Development of in-house AI systems

The development, training and operation of our own AI systems form part of the MfN's scientific remit. This may in future also include the development of our own language models.

The following apply to these activities:

- good scientific practice
- data protection checks
- project-related documentation

AI systems used exclusively for research purposes fall under the exemptions of the EU AI Regulation. A transition to productive or public use requires a separate assessment.

8. For an open museum

Transparency is essential for building trust in the MfN's scientific, administrative and communication processes. Disclosing the use of AI ensures traceability, safeguards institutional credibility and supports compliance with scientific and ethical standards.

Legal framework

Bei substanziellem Einsatz von KI ist der KI-Einsatz kenntlich zu machen, insbesondere bei Veröffentlichungen und Inhalten mit Außenwirkung.

Recommendations

- Document the use of AI in relevant work outputs.
- Make the use of AI transparent in external publications if it has had a significant impact on the content.
- Follow subject-specific standards and recommendations (e.g. COPE, WAME, DFG).
- Label AI-generated content appropriately (e.g. "AI-generated using [tool/model]" or "AI-assisted using [tool/model]").
- Ensure that staff and external parties are informed when they interact with AI-generated content or AI-supported systems (e.g. chatbots).

Examples

- In a scientific publication, the use of AI is described in the methods section or in the acknowledgements.
- In public relations, a corresponding note is added to AI-supported texts.

- Internal documents containing substantial use of AI include a brief note on the tool used and its purpose.

9. Developing together

The MfN promotes AI literacy among its staff through training courses, exchange forums and supporting materials.

Staff who use AI systems as part of their work should be given access to suitable training and information resources in accordance with the EU AI Regulation. These should cover the following aspects in particular:

- legal framework (GDPR, EU AI Regulation)
- safe and responsible use of AI systems
- quality assurance and verification of AI-generated content
- institutional requirements of this guideline

MfN's AI Working Group (KI AG) and other relevant bodies offer suitable training courses, information materials and discussion forums for this purpose (e.g. workshops, webinars, internal knowledge platforms).

For questions regarding the use of AI in relation to good scientific practice, the designated contact persons and ombudspersons are available as the first points of contact

10. Validity

The directive takes effect on May 22, 2026.

Director General

Management Director

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